

Mitigation of Secondary Blast Effects Using Tubular Structures

Noushad Bin Jamal M*, S Parthasarathy† M S Xavier†

*IIT Madras, Madras, TamilNadu, 600036.

† IIT Madras, Madras, TamilNadu, 600036.

† IIT Madras, Madras, TamilNadu, 600036.

Presenting author's email: am17m011@smail.iitm.ac.in, am17m006@smail.iitm.ac.in

Abstract

Mitigation of secondary blast effects on occupants in armored vehicles when subjected to mine blast has been explored by conducting numerical, analytical and experimental on circular as well as square aluminum (Al 6061) tubes. A parametric study on effect of thickness, diameter, obliquity of impact, boundary condition as well as relative rigidity of top plate connected to the tube were investigated. Modes of failure as well as performance matrices of crush efficiency were found to be consistent with the experimental observations.

1. Introduction

Armored vehicles which are subjected to mine blasts poses serious threats at different scales to occupants. Armor plating a vehicle is insufficient to protect the occupant against land mine explosions. Johnson and Reid (1978) have reviewed a large number of investigations pertaining to the subject of collapse of tubes and other structures. From the point of view of energy-absorption capacity. Abramowicz and Jones (1989) conducted a series of axial crushing tests on steel square tubes and observed three failure modes. These works have been revisited to investigate the dynamic crushing load capacity under secondary blast effects. Experimental study has been conducted to investigate the impulse transmitted and the average strain, strain rate.

2. Numerical Investigation

A dynamic analysis using explicit time integration scheme employed in Abaqus 6.11, a commercially available FEA package is used to simulate impact events and interpret the response of single as well as multiple tube sandwich type structures. Johnson-Cook material model has been adopted for both the failure as well as plastic model.

Figure (1) Combined mode of bending and symmetric lobe failure in four tube sandwich system

Figure (2.a) Relative Impulse Transmission

Figure (2.b) Efficiency Plot for 20 cm Tube

3. Analytical Investigation

Analytical expressions for crush force proposed by Abramowicz and Jones (1984) has been modified with popular Cowper Symond expression for dynamic yield stress. Results were close to the experimental as well as numerical counter parts. Theoretical dynamic modulus based on average strain rate has been calculated from experimental observations.

$$\text{Asymmetric mode A } P_m = 11.48 * \sigma_y^{dyn} * t^{\frac{5}{3}} b^{\frac{1}{3}} + 0.44 * \sigma_y^{dyn} * t^{\frac{4}{3}} b^{\frac{2}{3}} + 0.26 * \sigma_y^{dyn} * t^2 \quad (1)$$

4. Experimental Investigation

Samples were tested using drop weight test facility and the reaction force history is recorder to find the average strain rate, impact duration, impulse transmission, peak crush force and mean crush force. Deformation modes were closely matching with numerical observations.

Figure (3) Diamond mode failure in 15 cm long circular tube

Impact duration which governs the identification of impact event and further impulse calculations, was found to be very near to the numerical simulation results. Unlike conventional performance matrices, Impulse transmitted is considered as the key parameter which can be correlated with NATO HFM-090 standards.

5. Summary

It is observed that variation in total energy absorption between numerical and analytical was not significant in each case. Mean Crush Force was in similar ranges for both the square and circular tube case in analytical , Numerical and experimental studies. Variation in Specific Energy Absorption between analytical and numerical studies reveals that the simplified assumptions used in analytical model may not be fully satisfied in the numerical simulation. The Crush Force Efficiency clearly reveals that the circular cross sections are better in handling the energy absorptions. Further study on controlling the variation in crushing force can be done by introducing kinks, serrations, holes etc., in the tube structures to create the instability points.

6. References

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